

The Relationship between Transport Accessibility of Emergency Medical Care and Mortality Rates in Municipalities of the Central Federal District

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Received 20 January 2025 ♦ Accepted 27 July 2025 ♦ Published 25 September 2025

Citation: Lognenko MM (2025) The Relationship between Transport Accessibility of Emergency Medical Care and Mortality Rates in Municipalities of the Central Federal District. *Population and Economics* 9(2):127-152. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.9.e147200>

Abstract

In Russia, the most common causes of death are cardiovascular diseases at older ages and external causes at younger ages. In both cases, survival largely depends on the time elapsed between the onset of the condition or injury and the provision of medical assistance. Under federal legislation, every citizen of the Russian Federation has the right to receive emergency medical care in life-threatening situations. The aim of this paper is to examine the extent to which overall mortality rates depend on the response time of emergency medical services (EMS) at the municipal level in the Central Federal District. The main finding is that an increase in EMS response time is associated with higher mortality only within the first 10 minutes, and this pattern is observed primarily in municipalities with a high proportion of urban population. Significant intra-regional inequality in the accessibility of emergency medical care is also identified.

Keywords

emergency medical care, access to medical care, center-periphery inequality in mortality, travel time, municipalities, urbanization, crude mortality rate

JEL codes: I14, R41

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases and external causes are among the leading causes of death in Russia. In recent years, external causes have become the predominant cause of death at younger ages (up to 44 years for men and up to 39 years for women, excluding infant mortality), while beyond these ages cardiovascular diseases dominate (Figure 1). For both groups of causes,

the interval between the onset of the condition or exposure to external factors and the provision of medical care plays a crucial role in patient survival.

Figure 1. Distribution of deaths by cause across age groups, Russian Federation, 2019. *Source:* compiled by the author based on Rosstat data

In research on the organization of health care, the availability of medical services is understood as the outcome of a process consisting of:

1. the interaction between the characteristics of the health care system and those of its potential users, and
2. the regulation of this interaction by public policy (Khan and Bhardwaj 1994).

Accessibility of medical care is a multi-dimensional concept that encompasses not only transport, but also temporal, financial, organizational, informational and other factors. Owing to this complexity, accessibility as a whole is rarely studied in the literature, since it cannot be measured in its entirety; instead, individual components are usually examined. In the study by Khan and Bhardwaj (1994), two dimensions of accessibility are distinguished (each with two classes of measurement): potential versus realized, and spatial versus non-spatial.

Potential accessibility refers to the availability of health care resources in relation to the demand for their services, reflecting how the health care system responds to the characteristics of potential users. Realized accessibility captures the actual volume of health services delivered, and is shaped not only by potential accessibility but also by various barriers or facilitators within the health system and among its users (which may, in turn, generate unmet health care needs).

The spatial/non-spatial dimension distinguishes between physical (geographical) accessibility – the ability of potential users to reach a facility or specialist capable of providing the required service – and other factors such as economic constraints, social discrimination or lack of information. For research on emergency medical care, the spatial dimension is of

particular importance, since physical accessibility (measured, among other things, by the time required to receive care) plays a decisive role in the outcome of acute conditions, influencing both survival and the degree of rehabilitation. Accordingly, this article focuses on the transport component of emergency medical care accessibility.

In international studies on the relationship between the availability of emergency medical services (EMS) and mortality, ambulance response time has been found to be significantly associated with 30-day mortality following hospitalization: the longer the waiting time, the higher the likelihood of death within 30 days (Gold et al. 2010; Boniatti et al. 2014; Jena et al. 2017).

Delays in EMS provision are influenced by both geographical and non-geographical factors, with the latter contributing more strongly to pre-hospital delays (Pathak et al. 2011; Wodschow et al. 2021; Oyatani et al. 2023). Key geographical factors include the level of urbanisation (Zou et al. 2023), population density (Yasunaga et al. 2011), and urban–rural residence (Jordan et al. 2004; Timonin et al. 2018; Zou et al. 2023). Important non-geographical factors include patient age, the presence of witnesses at symptom onset (Oyatani et al. 2023), and income level (Pathak et al. 2011).

Studies of health care accessibility also identify areas that are underserved, or at risk of becoming underserved, which can then inform recommendations for local authorities (Jordan 2004; Messina et al. 2006; Patel et al. 2007; Sasaki et al. 2010; Yasunaga et al. 2011; Vanderschuren and McKune 2015; Wodschow et al. 2021).

At present, relatively few studies address the availability of medical care in Russia. Existing research has focused on primary health care (Kazantsev and Rummyantseva 2022), the provision of medical services and the functioning of the health system as a whole (Panin et al. 2023; Shartova et al. 2023), the accessibility of high-technology medical care (Timonin et al. 2018; Bulina et al. 2022), and the availability of inter-district medical centers (Medvedeva et al. 2019; Parfenova and Faleyshchik 2020). All of these studies reveal marked spatial heterogeneity in access to health care. However, no research has yet examined the relationship between EMS response time and mortality.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the extent to which overall mortality depends on EMS response time at the municipal level in the Central Federal District (CFD). The use of municipal data allows us to assess inequality in EMS accessibility not only between regions but also within regions.

Methods

The provision of emergency medical care in Russia is regulated by Order No. 388n of the Ministry of Health (Order of the Ministry of Health... 2013). According to this Order, emergency medical care is divided into two categories: emergency (where there is a threat to the patient's life) and urgent (where there is no immediate threat). For emergency cases, the maximum waiting time is set at 20 minutes. Accordingly, areas where the waiting time exceeds 20 minutes are considered insufficiently accessible. Calls for emergency medical assistance are made through the regional emergency communication system, and the nearest available ambulance team within the region is dispatched.

Current studies on health care accessibility typically employ the following measures:

- Straight-line distance from a settlement to the nearest health service provider (Jordan et al. 2004; Al-Taiar et al. 2010). This measure is used when road network data are un-

available. Both studies found a strong correlation between straight-line distance and actual travel time ($R^2 > 0.9$).

- Road network distance from a settlement to a health service provider (Pathak et al. 2011).
- Share of population/settlements within or beyond reach of a health facility within a specified time frame, usually estimated using isochrone methods (Patel et al. 2007; Fisher and Lassa 2017; Ihantamalala et al. 2020; Panin et al. 2023).
- Travel time from the location of the population (settlement or area unit) to the nearest facility (Vanderschuren and McKune 2015; Timonin et al. 2018; Oyatani et al. 2023).
- Two-Step Floating Catchment Area (2SFCA) models (Luo and Wang 2003). This approach accounts for both demand per unit of supply (system load at a given location) and supply per unit of demand (capacity available to each patient) (Mathon et al. 2018; Kazantsev and Rumyantseva 2022). At present, it is regarded as the most advanced method for assessing transport accessibility (to clinics, shops, etc.), as it captures supply–demand ratios, provider competition (depending on the modification), and heterogeneity in consumer characteristics and behaviour (Kazantsev and Rumyantseva 2022).

However, its application to EMS accessibility in Russia is problematic. At the municipal level, restrictions are primarily spatial rather than temporal: each station has its own service area defined by administrative boundaries, regardless of actual travel time. Under this system, EMS accessibility measured by the 2SFCA model would be identical for all settlements within the same municipality.

In this study, we use the time required for an ambulance to reach a patient from the nearest medical facility as an indicator of EMS availability, since it is the delay in time rather than the distance from the point of departure that affects patient mortality (Boniatti et al. 2014; Jena et al. 2017). Application of the 2SFCA model – although generally regarded as a more accurate measure of health service availability – is problematic in the context of emergency care, for the reasons outlined above.

The waiting time for medical assistance following an ambulance call can be divided into several stages (Figure 2). Researchers who adopt travel time from the nearest facility as an indicator of accessibility operationalize this measure differently, depending on the data available. For example, Oyatani et al. (2023) examined several intervals, including the time from symptom onset to hospital treatment, the time from symptom onset to hospital arrival, and the period from ambulance departure to hospital admission (time to patient + time providing assistance on site), using individual-level data from cardiovascular centers in Hokkaido. By contrast, Vanderschuren and McKune (2015) and Timonin et al. (2018) focused solely on travel time to the patient (highlighted in green in Figure 2), which they calculated using ArcGIS services.

Since individual-level data on ambulance calls were unavailable, we were only able to estimate the travel time from the nearest medical facility capable of dispatching an ambulance to the patient. It was not possible to account for subsequent transport from the patient to the hospital, as the patient is not necessarily taken to the same facility from which the ambulance was dispatched, but rather to the institution best equipped to provide care based on the diagnosis made by the attending ambulance doctor.

In previous studies where EMS accessibility was measured as travel time from the population location (settlement or area unit) to the nearest medical facility, both mean (Vander-

schuren and McKune 2015; Jena et al. 2017) and median waiting times (Timonin et al. 2018; Oyatani et al. 2023) have been employed as summary indicators of accessibility. In our study, we use the mean municipality-level ambulance arrival time as the final measure of EMS availability, as this approach accounts for possible outliers in the upper tail of the distribution – individuals experiencing exceptionally long waits, who are at the greatest risk of fatal outcomes due to delays in receiving emergency medical care. The distribution of median EMS travel times across municipalities of the Central Federal District is provided in the Appendix (Figure A3).

This study uses data for the Central Federal District (CFD) in 2019. The CFD was selected as the focus of analysis because it is the most populous, economically developed and strategically important part of the country, while also displaying pronounced heterogeneity in mortality rates (Fattakhov and Mironova 2022). In 2019, the cause-of-death structure in the CFD mirrored that of Russia as a whole: external causes dominated mortality at younger ages, whereas diseases of the circulatory system were the leading cause of death at older ages (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Stages of waiting for emergency medical services. *Note:* The stage highlighted in green is the focus of this study. *Source:* compiled by the author

Figure 3. Distribution of deaths by cause across age groups, Central Federal District, 2019. *Source:* compiled by the author based on Rosstat data

This study uses data for 2019, the last year without mortality anomalies caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (2020–2021) and the last year for which population distribution data can be regarded as reliable. The demographic research community has questioned the quality of the 2020 population census, and from 2021 onwards population distribution estimates are based on those census results (Andreev and Churilova 2023). Other Russian spatial studies of health care accessibility have also focused on 2019 (Fattakhov and Mironova 2022; Kazantsev and Rumyantseva 2022; Panin et al. 2023).

The algorithm for calculating EMS accessibility was as follows:

1. **Population distribution database.** A set of geographic coordinates with the corresponding population counts was compiled, following the methodology of the CPUR study on primary health care accessibility (Kazantsev and Rumyantseva 2022). The sources used were Populated Areas of Russia: Population Size and Geographic Coordinates and the location of precinct election commissions (PECs) databases provided by the RCSI project. The distribution of the population of the Central Federal District by settlement size is presented in the Appendix (Figure P4).
2. **Database of medical facilities capable of dispatching ambulances.** Following Kazantsev and Rumyantseva (2022), the Federal Register of Medical Organizations provided by the Ministry of Health was used (Federal Register... 2022–2023). The database included individual EMS stations and substations, EMS stations located at central district and regional hospitals, and in regional centers, specialized EMS hospitals or hospitals authorized to provide emergency care in the absence of dedicated EMS hospitals.
3. **Travel time estimation.** For each populated location, the ambulance arrival time was calculated from the nearest medical facility in the same region (since dispatch networks are organized at the regional level). Calculations were based on the OpenStreet-Map service, with selected routes verified using Yandex Maps.
4. **Municipal-level aggregation.** Mean ambulance arrival times were calculated for first-level municipalities (municipal districts, urban districts, and urban districts with intra-city divisions).
5. **Statistical analysis.** Using municipal socio-economic statistics (DBMI), the relationship between overall mortality and EMS accessibility was calculated and analyzed.

Moscow was excluded from the analysis because its population size and resources are not comparable with those of other regions, and its ambulance routing system is highly complex. For example, hospitals alternate in receiving ambulance patients depending on the day of the week, a pattern that cannot be captured with the available data. Closed administrative–territorial entities (for which only limited municipal statistics are available) and districts abolished in 2019 (since municipal statistics are reported by territory at the end of the year) were also excluded. In total, the analysis covered exactly 500 municipalities.

Work restrictions

This study employs a simulated indicator – the average waiting time for emergency medical care – calculated on the basis of the theoretical distribution of the population across the Central Federal District in 2019. It is assumed that an ambulance will be dispatched from the nearest medical facility within the region that is capable of providing such a service. In prac-

tice, however, this assumption may not hold. A specialized team may be dispatched instead, departing from a more distant facility, or, if all teams at the nearest facility are occupied, an ambulance from another institution may be sent.

Furthermore, it is not possible to track the destination of the patient after the ambulance call, nor to estimate the probability that the patient will be transported at all. A more accurate assessment would require individual-level data on ambulance calls, including the time of call receipt, dispatch, arrival at the patient's location, and arrival at the hospital, as well as information on the patient's age and the reason for the call.

The tools used to calculate ambulance travel times also have limitations. They do not account for real-time traffic conditions, which can be a decisive factor in waiting times. Moreover, OpenStreetMap data may not fully reflect the actual road network in rural areas of Russia. Urban-specific barriers – such as gates, closed courtyards, and the lack of parking spaces – are also not considered, although they may significantly affect ambulance access.

Results and discussion

Based on the calculations, we constructed a distribution of emergency medical service travel times for populated areas of the Central Federal District, excluding Moscow (Table 1, Figures 4–6).

Figure 4 and Table 1 show that the majority of residents of the Central Federal District can access emergency medical care within the established standard of 20 minutes (indicated by the red line). However, 10.57% of the population – approximately 2.8 million people – live outside this zone. At the regional level, this share ranges from 3.9% in Moscow Oblast to 19.4% in Tambov Oblast (Figure 5). This distribution reflects the fact that most of the population of the Central Federal District resides in cities or regional centers, which are typically located close to hospitals or emergency medical stations.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of waiting times for emergency medical services in the Central Federal District, 2019

Emergency medical services arrival time in municipalities	
Mode	3.5
Median	5.25
Standard deviation	9.42
Dispersion	88.78
Standard error	0.00183
First quartile	3.15
Third quartile	9.8
First decile	2
Ninth decile	20.8
Minimum	0
Maximum	282

Source: compiled by the author.

Figure 4. Distribution of waiting times for emergency medical services by population size of municipalities in the Central Federal District, 2019 (minutes). *Source:* compiled by the author

Figure 5. Percentage of the population living beyond a 20-minute reach of emergency medical services by region, Central Federal District. *Source:* compiled by the author

Figure 6 indicates that the most problematic areas are located along the northern borders of the Central Federal District, where numerous villages are situated and the transport network is poorly developed (e.g. Tver and Kostroma oblasts, the shores of the Rybinsk Reservoir in Yaroslavl Oblast). Other problematic areas are found in the interior of regions, at equal distances from several regional centers (e.g. Kantemirovsky District in Voronezh Oblast, parts of Tver Oblast, and the Meshchersky forest reserve zone between Moscow,

Vladimir, and Ryazan). In such cases, access to a hospital in a neighboring region would be faster, but this is not possible because emergency call reception networks operate strictly within regional boundaries. The highest concentration of medical facilities is observed in Moscow Oblast.

Figure 6. Distribution of waiting times for emergency medical services in the Central Federal District (minutes). *Note:* medical organizations are indicated by blue dots. *Source:* compiled by the author

Table 2 and Figures 7–8 show that, at the municipal level, the average travel time for emergency medical services is distributed differently from that at the level of individual settlements. The municipal-level distribution is more centralized, with a median value of about 12.5 minutes and considerably lower dispersion. However, in 46 municipalities (9.2% of the total), the average waiting time for emergency medical services exceeds the 20-minute standard.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of average waiting times for emergency medical services in municipalities of the Central Federal District (in minutes)

Emergency medical services arrival time in municipalities	
Average	12.33
Standard error	0.26
Median	12.22
Standard deviation	5.75
Sample variance	33.11
Minimum	1.81
Maximum	34.00
Number of observations (N)	500

Source: compiled by the author.

Figure 7. Distribution of waiting time for emergency medical services in the Central Federal District (in minutes). *Source:* compiled by the author

Figure 8. Distribution of waiting time for emergency medical services in the Central Federal District (in minutes). *Source:* compiled by the author

Although most residents of the Central Federal District live in cities, the share of “urban” municipalities (urban districts) is relatively small – only 17.4% of those examined. In contrast, in “non-urban” municipalities (other types of municipalities), the average travel

time for emergency medical services is noticeably higher. This disparity is particularly pronounced in cases where the district center is separated into an independent city administration. For example, in the city of Kimry (Tver Oblast), the average ambulance arrival time is 5.7 minutes, whereas in the surrounding Kimry District it reaches 34 minutes.

Overall, in 46 municipalities the average travel time for emergency medical services exceeds the 20-minute standard. Only Kaluga and Moscow Oblasts have no municipalities exceeding this threshold (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Share of municipalities with an average EMS waiting time exceeding 20 minutes, by region of the Central Federal District. *Source:* compiled by the author

At present, the crude death rate (CDR) is the only mortality indicator available at the municipal level in Russia that can be obtained from open sources, such as the Database of Municipal Indicators. The same database also provides the age structure of each municipality’s population, which allows calculation of standardized mortality rates using the indirect standardization method. However, in this study, the CDR was chosen as the mortality indicator because using a standardized measure would remove the influence of age structure, which also affects ambulance travel times: municipalities with older populations have a higher probability of emergency calls and, consequently, a greater load on EMS. To address potential bias in model coefficients, the CDR is used as the outcome variable, while age structure is included as a covariate, defined as the proportion of the population aged 65 years and older. This approach – analyzing raw rates with age as a covariate rather than using standardized scores – is recommended in the literature (Rosenbaum and Rubin 1984).

Figure 10 illustrates the distribution of municipal crude death rates (CDR) in relation to average EMS waiting times. At the level of the entire Central Federal District, a positive association between ambulance waiting time and mortality is apparent; however, this relationship is observed primarily within the first 10 minutes and is most pronounced in municipalities with predominantly urban populations.

Figure 10. Relationship between the crude death rate and average EMS waiting time (minutes) in municipalities of the Central Federal District, differentiated by the proportion of the urban population. *Note:* circles indicate outliers that were excluded from the analysis. *Source:* compiled by the author

Based on Figure 10, the following hypothesis can be proposed: an increase in average EMS waiting time is positively associated with the municipal crude death rate (CDR) only within the first 10 minutes, primarily in municipalities with a high proportion of urban population. In predominantly rural municipalities, ambulances may not arrive in time to affect outcomes, and mortality is likely influenced by factors other than EMS availability.

To test this hypothesis, econometric models were estimated using the generalized least squares (GLS) method, as the analysis was based on aggregated data for a single year. Robust standard errors were employed to account for heteroscedasticity, as indicated by the Breusch–Pagan test. Outliers were excluded to improve model accuracy, specifically municipalities with CDR values above 30‰ or below 5‰, as well as the city of Shchigry in Kursk Oblast (CDR 20.7‰, average ambulance waiting time 2.4 minutes).

To further ensure robustness and avoid diluting the effect due to varying shares of urban population, additional variables were included:

- An indicator variable for municipalities with average ambulance travel time below 10 minutes (1 if < 10 minutes, 0 otherwise), applied only to the full sample.
- Average EMS travel time for populations living outside the 10-minute transport accessibility zone, to capture the influence of the upper tail of the travel time distribution.
- The share of the population residing within 10 minutes of EMS accessibility.

The analysis was conducted for three groups of municipalities:

- all municipalities;
- municipalities with average EMS travel time greater than 10 minutes;
- municipalities with average EMS travel time less than 10 minutes.

The inclusion of the additional variable – average EMS travel time for populations living outside the 10-minute transport accessibility zone – requires that the municipality contains

at least one population point located beyond this zone. Consequently, municipalities entirely within the 10-minute EMS accessibility zone were excluded from calculations involving this variable. Since all excluded municipalities have an average EMS travel time below 10 minutes, two additional groups of municipalities were defined to allow for a more accurate comparison of the models:

- All municipalities with at least one population point for which EMS travel time exceeds 10 minutes.
- Municipalities with an average EMS travel time below 10 minutes, but containing at least one population point where EMS travel time exceeds 10 minutes.

In total, five groups of municipalities were defined. For municipalities with average EMS travel times above and below 10 minutes, five models were estimated for each group:

- Without the variable of interest (average EMS waiting time) or any additional variables.
- Including the variable of interest, but without additional variables.
- Including the variable of interest along with each additional variable separately: average EMS travel time for populations living outside the 10-minute EMS accessibility zone, share of the population residing within the 10-minute EMS accessibility zone.
- Including the variable of interest together with both additional variables.
- For the full sample of municipalities, an additional indicator variable was introduced for municipalities with average EMS travel times below 10 minutes. This variable was interacted with the main variable of interest (average EMS waiting time). In total, 11 models were estimated for the full sample.

Within each group of municipalities, model performance was evaluated using the adjusted coefficient of determination (adjusted R^2), the Akaike information criterion (AIC), and the Bayesian information criterion (BIC). The best-fitting model for each group was then selected based on these criteria.

The following factors were considered as potentially significant determinants of municipal mortality rates:

- Age structure of the population (proportion aged 65+). As noted above, age structure is a key determinant of the overall (non-standardized) mortality rate: municipalities with older populations exhibit higher CDRs (Yasunaga et al. 2011; Kazantsev and Romyantseva 2022).
- Degree of urbanization (proportion of urban population). Numerous studies indicate that urbanization, as a proxy for territorial development, is an important geographical factor affecting EMS delays (Jordan et al. 2004; Yasunaga et al. 2011; Timonin et al. 2018; Zou et al. 2023). In addition, rural areas with low population density tend to have older populations, which are associated with higher mortality rates (Yasunaga et al. 2011).
- Education level of the population (derived from the 2020 census). Despite potential discrepancies with 2019 data, this source is closer in time to the study year than the previous census of 2010. Higher educational attainment has been linked to lower mortality, particularly among ages 30–69, and is a significant predictor of municipal CDR (Kharkova et al. 2017; Kazantsev and Romyantseva 2022).
- Income level of the population (calculated as the ratio of average employee salary to the regional subsistence minimum, adjusting for regional price levels). Household income influences EMS waiting times (Pathak et al. 2011) and has a pronounced effect

on mortality in countries with average life expectancy, including Russia (Kolosnitsyna et al. 2019).

- Healthcare provision (number of medical and preventive care organizations (MPO) per 10.000 inhabitants).
- Regional characteristics (dummy variables for each region). Previous studies highlight regional heterogeneity in mortality levels, dynamics, and centre-periphery inequalities, as well as the role of regional healthcare system characteristics in shaping mortality (Shchur and Timonin 2020; Kossova 2023).

Although previous studies highlight the influence of lifestyle factors (Shalnova et al. 2005; Kossova 2023), as well as healthcare expenditure and the capacity of medical institutions (Kossova 2023), on mortality from cardiovascular diseases – whose contribution to overall mortality is closely linked to access to emergency medical care – the DBMI database does not include indicators for these factors. The only relevant measure available for 2019 is healthcare provision, expressed as the number of medical and preventive care organizations (MPO) per 10.000 inhabitants.

It would be possible, as in Kazantsev and Rumyantseva (2022), to include the unemployment rate; however, this indicator has several limitations. Firstly, it does not account for employees of small and medium-sized enterprises. Secondly, it fails to capture inter-municipal labor migration – for example, residents of neighboring municipalities working in a large production facility, who earn income in one municipality but spend it in another. For these reasons, the unemployment rate was not considered.

Climate data were also excluded, as the Central Federal District has a relatively uniform moderate climate, and 2019 did not experience extreme summer heatwaves or severe winter frosts. Descriptive statistics for all variables used are provided in the Appendix (Table A1). The correlation matrix for these characteristics is also available (Figures A1–A2). Full regression results for all groups of municipalities are presented in the Supplementary materials.

The results of the analysis are presented in Table 3. The proportion of elderly residents is a decisive determinant of municipal CDR: municipalities with higher shares of older population exhibit higher CDRs, all else being equal. Income level is also significant across all models, with higher average income associated with lower CDRs. In all models, CDR is significantly influenced by regional affiliation variables.

Where education level is significant, it is negatively associated with CDR, indicating that municipalities with a more educated population tend to have lower crude death rates, controlling for other factors. Interestingly, in all models where both the provision of medical and preventive care organizations (MPO) and the proportion of urban population are significant, they are positively associated with CDR. This pattern may reflect reverse causality: higher mortality may drive increased demand for MPO, resulting in more facilities within a municipality. Similarly, urban areas may attract older and less healthy populations due to better access to medical care, which in turn elevates mortality rates in cities.

Based on the modelling results, the hypothesis is partially confirmed. In the best-fitting model explaining the relationship between EMS availability and municipal CDR for all municipalities, the variable “average EMS travel time” alone is not significant. It becomes significant with a positive coefficient only when interacted with the indicator variable for municipalities where the average travel time is less than 10 minutes. This indicates that average EMS travel time is positively associated with CDR only within the first 10 minutes. The indicator variable itself is also significant and negatively associated with CDR, implying that,

all else being equal, municipalities with average EMS travel times below 10 minutes experience lower mortality than those where average travel times exceed 10 minutes.

In the best-fitting model for municipalities with average EMS travel times below 10 minutes, the average EMS travel time is significantly and positively associated with CDR.

Conversely, in the best model for municipalities with average EMS travel times above 10 minutes, average EMS travel time is negatively associated with CDR – meaning that shorter ambulance travel times are linked to higher mortality. A similar pattern is observed in the model for all municipalities that include at least one settlement where the ambulance travel time exceeds 10 minutes.

Interestingly, in the best model for municipalities containing at least one settlement with EMS travel times above 10 minutes, the additional variable representing average EMS travel time for populations located outside the 10-minute transport accessibility zone shows a significant positive coefficient. This suggests that the extended waiting times in these more remote settlements capture the positive effect of long EMS travel times on CDR.

This counterintuitive result – as well as the unexpected positive associations observed for the share of urban population and the provision of MPO – can likely be attributed to the uneven spatial distribution of demand for medical services across different groups of municipalities, depending on average EMS travel time. Municipalities with average EMS travel times below 10 minutes tend to have a high proportion of urban population and are typically relatively developed, economically active areas. These municipalities generally attract a younger, working-age population, and no counterintuitive patterns are observed in the signs of the other variables.

In contrast, municipalities with average ambulance travel times exceeding 10 minutes tend to have a higher proportion of rural, predominantly elderly populations. All counterintuitive results are characteristic of this group. These municipalities may also contain small cities or urban-type settlements where key regional infrastructure is concentrated; however, economic opportunities are limited, and the standard of living is similar to that of surrounding rural areas. Such settlements tend to attract residents who require access to infrastructure within walking distance, including individuals with health problems, which in turn increases local demand for medical services.

Table 3. Results of OLS regression on the factors of CDR in municipalities with average ambulance waiting times below and above 10 minutes

	All municipalities		Municipalities with average waiting time > 10 min		Municipalities with average waiting time < 10 min
	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Limiting the sample to the presence of settlements with travel time > 10 min					
Average waiting time for emergency medical services	-0.061 (0.059)	-0.080* (0.016)	0.215* (0.040)	0.156 (0.136)	-0.098* (0.018)
Dummy $\bar{t} < 10$	-2.648*** (<0.001)				

	All municipalities		Municipalities with average waiting time > 10 min		Municipalities with average waiting time < 10 min
\bar{t} for those who have $t_i > 10$		0.057*		0.024	0.049
		(0.013)		(0.613)	(0.151)
Dummy $\bar{t} < 10 \times$ Average emergency medical service arrival time	0.273***				
	(<0.001)				
Constant	9.825***	9.723***	8.735**	11.949**	9.515***
	(<0.001)	(<0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(<0.001)
Provision of medical and preventive organisations (MPO)	0.103***	0.098***	0.050	0.075+	0.105***
	(<0.001)	(<0.001)	(0.272)	(0.085)	(<0.001)
Average salary adjusted for the cost of living	-0.588***	-0.772***	-0.524*	-0.983***	-0.756**
	(<0.001)	(<0.001)	(0.032)	(<0.001)	(0.010)
Level of education	-0.013***	-0.012***	-0.015***	-0.011*	-0.010
	(<0.001)	(<0.001)	(<0.001)	(0.012)	(0.090)
Share of urban population	1.035*	0.353	0.268	0.333	0.690
	(0.035)	(0.467)	(0.852)	(0.821)	(0.282)
Proportion of population aged 65+	55.061***	53.072***	51.475***	40.853***	54.122***
	(<0.001)	(<0.001)	(<0.001)	(<0.001)	(<0.001)
Belgorod region	0.450	0.685	-0.405	-0.851	1.176
	(0.341)	(0.152)	(0.421)	(0.225)	(0.093)
Bryansk region	0.011	-0.068	0.072	-0.824	-0.139
	(0.986)	(0.916)	(0.933)	(0.434)	(0.885)
Vladimir region	1.191*	1.382*	1.845	1.549	1.142
	(0.035)	(0.015)	(0.060)	(0.113)	(0.162)
Voronezh region	-1.479**	-1.505**	-0.681	-1.884	-1.489
	(0.006)	(0.005)	(0.606)	(0.148)	(0.057)
Ivanovo region	0.939	0.896	0.909	0.002	1.016
	(0.109)	(0.165)	(0.118)	(0.998)	(0.305)
Kaluga region	-0.222	-0.112	0.797	0.792	-0.897
	(0.681)	(0.840)	(0.090)	(0.182)	(0.268)
Kursk region	3.964***	4.187***	2.721	2.260	4.304***
	(<0.001)	(<0.001)	(0.067)	(0.317)	(<0.001)
Kostroma region	0.916	0.337	0.350	-1.065	0.836
	(0.165)	(0.647)	(0.679)	(0.422)	(0.410)
Lipetsk region	0.928	0.911	0.455	-0.405	1.046
	(0.094)	(0.109)	(0.607)	(0.708)	(0.180)

	All municipalities		Municipalities with average waiting time > 10 min		Municipalities with average waiting time < 10 min
Moscow region	1.580** (0.001)	1.900*** (<0.001)	1.347** (0.005)	1.358* (0.027)	2.024 (0.122)
Orel region	0.612 (0.277)	0.696 (0.250)	0.576 (0.511)	-0.600 (0.518)	0.614 (0.456)
Ryazan region	-0.907 (0.078)	-0.726 (0.166)	-0.309 (0.600)	-0.569 (0.444)	-0.800 (0.306)
Smolensk region	1.257* (0.032)	1.172 (0.051)	0.847 (0.157)	-0.076 (0.918)	1.515 (0.112)
Tambov region	-0.132 (0.787)	-0.217 (0.678)	-0.228 (0.762)	-1.381 (0.247)	0.018 (0.980)
Tver region	1.246* (0.015)	1.154* (0.029)	2.364* (0.010)	2.501* (0.013)	0.915 (0.217)
Tula region	0.930 (0.066)	1.092* (0.025)	0.883 (0.176)	1.216* (0.016)	1.015 (0.188)
Number of observations	496	452	176	132	320
R2	0.698	0.671	0.771	0.807	0.573
R2 Adj.	0.683	0.653	0.738	0.766	0.540
AIC	1994.2	1828.3	646.3	474.6	1341.6
BIC	2103.6	1931.1	722.4	546.7	1435.8
RMSE	1.71	1.73	1.32	1.21	1.82

Source: compiled by the author. Note: Yaroslavl region is a region for comparison. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$; p-values for each coefficient are shown in parentheses.

Conclusion

This paper investigates the relationship between the availability of emergency medical care and the crude death rate (CDR) at the municipal level in the Central Federal District in 2019. Emergency medical care availability was measured using the average waiting time for an ambulance to reach a patient in each municipality.

The analysis shows that average ambulance waiting time is positively associated with overall mortality only within the first 10 minutes, and this effect is observed predominantly in municipalities with a high proportion of urban population. It is hypothesised that this pattern reflects differences in EMS availability between urban and non-urban municipalities: in non-urban areas, emergency medical services are often unable to reach patients in time, and CDR is therefore determined primarily by other factors.

This hypothesis was tested using linear regression models applied to the full sample as well as to subsamples of municipalities with average ambulance travel times below and above 10 minutes. A significant positive association at the 5% level was found only for mu-

nicipalities with average ambulance travel times below 10 minutes, indicating that longer ambulance arrival times are associated with higher CDR. Conversely, in municipalities with average ambulance travel times exceeding 10 minutes, the relationship with CDR is significant at the 5% level but negative, likely reflecting that district centres in these municipalities attract residents who require regular access to medical services, rather than primarily the economically active population.

Across all models, CDR is strongly associated with the proportion of elderly residents, income levels, and regional healthcare characteristics. In municipalities with average EMS waiting times below 10 minutes, the education level of the population also emerges as a significant factor. In municipalities with average EMS waiting times exceeding 10 minutes, the availability of medical and preventive care facilities and the proportion of urban population are additionally significant.

A clear centre–periphery inequality in access to emergency medical care was observed across the regions of the Central Federal District. This finding aligns with previous Russian studies on mortality (Shchur and Timonin 2020; Fattakhov and Mironova 2022) and healthcare accessibility (Timonin et al. 2018; Kazantsev and Rumyantseva 2022; Panin et al. 2023), which similarly identified intraregional disparities in mortality rates, partly attributable to unequal access to medical services.

For patients with urgent, potentially life-threatening conditions, an ambulance must reach them within 10 minutes. As of 2019, excluding Moscow, 24.18% of the population in the Central Federal District – over 6.5 million people – resided beyond a 10-minute reach of emergency medical stations and hospitals. Additionally, 2.8 million people, or 10.57% of the population excluding Moscow, lived beyond the 20-minute accessibility threshold established by the Ministry of Health.

The following directions may be pursued in future research on the availability of emergency medical services (EMS):

- Addressing and correcting the limitations identified in this study, including the use of individual-level EMS call data, more precise mapping (e.g., Yandex maps accounting for traffic congestion), and improved population distribution data.
- Extending the analysis to other regions, where additional factors such as climate or low territorial development may influence EMS accessibility.
- Conducting studies using post-pandemic data to assess the impact of EMS organisational reforms and changes induced by COVID-19 between 2020 and 2024.
- Employing machine learning approaches to model EMS supply capacity in greater detail (e.g., load per EMS vehicle) (Aringhieri et al. 2017; Bélanger et al. 2020), and to explore potential nonlinear relationships between mortality and EMS availability (Karlsson et al. 2021; Chang et al. 2023).
- Undertaking a more detailed investigation of the relationship between average ambulance waiting time and mortality in municipalities where average EMS arrival times exceed 10 minutes.

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Acknowledgments

Author would like to thank Evgeny Materov and Timofey Samsonov for the open source online tutorials that made the implementation of the methodology possible.

Supplementary material

Regression results for municipalities' groups

Distribution of waiting times for emergency medical services by region, by municipalities (average waiting time for emergency medical services) and populated areas

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.9.e147200.suppl>

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Appendix

Table A1. Descriptive statistics of selected control variables by municipality

	CDR	Number of medical and preventive institutions per 10 thousand population	Average monthly salary (excluding MP)/ subsistence level
Average	16.63	10.09	3.72
Standard error	0.15	0.33	0.05
Median	16.50	9.28	3.45
Standard deviation	3.28	7.34	1.09
Sample variance	10.78	53.94	1.19
Minimum	4.90	0.00	2.21
Maximum	31.40	38.51	11.75
N	500	500	500
	Proportion of population 65+	Share of urban population	Population with higher education 2020, ‰
Average	0.17	0.50	143.70
Standard error	0.00	0.01	1.96
Median	0.17	0.50	134.78
Standard deviation	0.03	0.32	43.74
Sample variance	0.00	0.11	1913.28
Minimum	0.03	0.00	61.02
Maximum	0.26	1.00	319.47
N	500	500	500

	Average waiting time for emergency medical services	The share of the population living within 10 minutes of transport accessibility of EMS	Average EMS travel time for the population living outside the 10-minute accessibility zone
Average	12.33	0.597415	24.01256
Standard error	0.26	0.010271	0.318951
Median	12.22	0.580321	23.8451
Standard deviation	5.75	0.229667	6.810927
Sample variance	33.11	0.052747	46.38873
Minimum	1.81	0	10.1
Maximum	34.00	1	52.98948
N	500	500	456

**Indicator variable of a municipality in which
the average waiting time for EMS is less than
10 minutes**

Average	0.358
Standard error	0.021461
Median	0
Standard deviation	0.479892
Sample variance	0.230297
Minimum	0
Maximum	1
N	500

Figure A1. Correlation matrix of selected factors, excluding regional dummy variables

Figure A2. Correlation matrix of selected factors, including regional dummy variables

Figure A3. Median waiting time for emergency medical services in municipalities of the Central Federal District. *Note:* The green coloring of the northern parts of Kostroma and Tver regions is explained by the high concentration of population in cities and regional centers

Figure A4. Distribution of the population in the Central Federal District by settlement size